

Abstract

Is synchronicity a real phenomenon or an illusion that inevitably leads to delusion? Here, I define synchronicity, discuss it and argue that it is a real phenomenon, but also explain why it may be hard to understand and accept it as such.

Understanding synchronicity

Mario Ljubičić (completerelativity.org)

108. brigade ZNG 43, 35252 Sibinj, Croatia mljubic99@gmail.com

October 8, 2025

1 Introduction

Many are still sceptical about synchronicity, which C. G. Jung defined as "meaningful coincidence of two or more events where something other than the probability of chance is involved".

The scepticism is not surprising - regular experience of synchronicity is not common, it cannot be forced and therefore often cannot be replicated in controlled environment. Many (such as D. J. Hand[1]) claim that these coincidences are meaningless and can be fully explained by probability calculus.

Prior to year ~2017 that was precisely my view, but then I've experienced a physiological transformation and started experiencing synchronicity regularly. Quickly, it became obvious that the odds for the experienced synchronicity being a random coincidence are infinitesimal.

Synchronicity seems to be highly correlated with mentality and lack of force. It is deeply correlated with subconsciousness[2] and long-term operation rather than conscious short-term [re]actions of force. Experiences of synchronicity should thus be growing with growing number of non-polarized[3] people, making it even harder to dismiss as meaningless coincidence.

Episodes of overwhelming synchronicity, however, are linked to psychosis[4] and may be *dangerous* for some people (mostly because they are in an environment that treats people experiencing synchronicity as patients).

However, those whose minds survive this *psychosis* generally become different people than they were before. This change seems to be generally positive, increasing well-being and overall understanding of nature by the individual. One of my hypotheses is that such transformation is, in fact, transformation of a polarized mind into a neutral one - enabling development of strongly focused, rational and unbiased thoughts. But this isn't just a transformation of consciousness, it involves changes in

both body and mind.

But even random coincidence is still relatively meaningless - if it is, for example, interpreted as meaningful and changes the course of one's life, obviously it wasn't absolutely meaningless.

Meaning, however, is not only very relative, but it is usually an personal/-subjective interpretation. From scientific perspective, synchronicity can have value if it is not a random co-incident of events. But again, with no absolute certainty, and with no ability to uncover hidden variables, randomness inevitably becomes a probabilistic variable. I usually treat any apparently non-random coincidence as meaningful synchronicity - where the odds of random coincidence are sufficiently small. The odds are quantifiable, but what is considered "sufficiently small" can be a personal choice or a matter of consensus of a broader community (e.g., sigma thresholds in modern science). Synchronicity can thus be a religious experience but should not be generally ignored by scientific community just because some (or even most) cases can be explained through statistics.

There is no apparent causal connection between synchronized phenomena in synchronicity. There are two interpretations of this. Either the correlation does not require causal connection (as in conventional interpretations of quantum entanglement), or there are hidden variables. In any case, one can assume the existence of some kind of a field and an attractor in it about which the correlated phenomena may clump in space/time. The assumption of the existence of fields is common in physics, even though none of the, so called, fundamental fields are directly observable. Salient difference between a gravitational field, for example, and a field associated with synchronicity is that the latter is a more general field of information correlation, while the former is a subfield of that general field (correlating information associated solely with mass/energy).

With relativity in cause and effect, postulated by Complete Relativity[5] (CR), connection between any correlated phenomena cannot be absolutely observable. Physical links not observable on one scale are observable on a different scale.

Mental connections are generally non-observable. Non-observable connections in meaningful synchronicity may be interpreted as mental connections, but, in CR, even mental connections (or pathways for information exchange) are physical at some scale. That scale is simply unobservable from our perspective due to intrinsic limitations of observers. The limitations are required for the existence.

Furthermore, from my own experience, I have found many events that happened long ago (which, considered alone, had no significant meaning at the

time) deeply correlated with events happened to me in the future (providing significant meaning to the past event), implying strong determinism in local evolution (equivalent to genetic coding in standard lifeforms).

Thus, what one considers meaningless at one point in time could become meaningful at some other point in time. I refer to such events as signals of synchronicity or signs. With rising experience in synchronicity, one could recognize potential signs and perhaps predict certain future events. Again, however, the recognition and interpretation of these signals can be more religious or more scientific, depending on the experience and the method of deduction. In any case, this is a domain of stochastic mathematics.

It appears that nature is interpreting time as a dimension of space, so just like points separated in space, points separated in time exist simultaneously. The moment of now can be interpreted as a superposition of past and future. The experience of now is a simultaneous experience of past and future. The reason we usually cannot see far into the future is the strong focus of consciousness - shortening the moment of now. In other words, the superposition/experience of past and future is, for us, strongly localized. Mathematically, this can be interpreted as wavefunction collapse. Consciousness can be delocalized, at which point the experience may be stretched far into the past and future, but this doesn't appear to be something we can usually control. I hypothesize, however, that deeper levels of consciousness are less localized, and this is why synchronicity is highly correlated with subconscious. The experience of synchronicity may thus be a signal that we are being controlled or guided by our subconscious. Overwhelming synchronicity and associated behaviour (sometimes interpreted as psychosis) is then probably a signal that our subconscious has *taken the wheel*. Indeed, after I have survived overwhelming synchronicity, I can confidently say now that at the time I was *not my self*. This explains why people who experience this commonly behave like prophets during the time. At least some of their prophecies are probably true. The dates, however, are unlikely to be true. Why? Because to these prophets the future is in the moment of now, so they will use dates close to the present. I know I did, but I am not alone. Even one of the most famous prophets, J. Christ, announced the apocalypse *just about the corner*.

With the current state of climate and the environment, many of us feel the apocalypse now really is, or very close to being, *just about the corner*. Paradoxically, in order for this kind of prophecies to become true, the serious prophets must not be taken seriously. In order for the prophecy of Christ to be fulfilled, for example, the Christians must not follow the Christ, for the prophet was - with his humble life - working against the prophecy, or at least was not contributing to its realization. Apparently, the determinism in local evolution is so strong that people are convinced they have no choice but to follow the money. I guess a god on a dollar bill is there to fool their subconscious into thinking that, by following the

money, they follow the Christ. Ignorance of subconscious/synchronicity is the ignorance of future [and past]. This might sound like preaching, but no, I do not consider that ignorance as something absolutely bad. By sacrificing the prophet/subconscious, people might have sacrificed their future human nature, because once the subconscious is lost, nothing will prevent the *annihilation* of human nature. But I believe their lives will go on, albeit in a less complex form, actually more adapted to short-term interests. They won't be able to infinitely grow and do much harm with subdued cognition. In other words, they will have no choice but to be good for the planet. I don't see the choice between the *Christ* and money as a choice between the good and bad. I see it as a choice between the freedom of the mind and preservation of the physical body. Absolute freedom of the mind is absolute death, absolute preservation of the body is absolute lack of mind. Neither is possible. Personally, I have been oscillating significantly between the sides, but I believe I am destined to settle somewhere in between because that is what I seem to desire.

2 Definitions

2.1 Synchronization

Synchronization of events is simultaneous occurrence of events. Simultaneous occurrence (synchronization) can be forced (causal) or non-forced (acausal), although the interpretation is relative. Events can be synchronized in time (localized to the same point in time) and/or space (localized to the same point in space). Strength or magnitude of synchronization is proportional to its localization.

Note, however, one may choose to make a distinction between events and phenomena, with localization in space being synchronization of phenomena, and synchronization in time being localization of events.

Apart from simultaneous occurrence, synchronized events can be more or less correlated in other ways.

Synchronization can be relatively self-sustaining, stable or unstable, transient or permanent, periodic or non-periodic. It may also transition from forced to non-forced synchronization.

Consider a person waking up daily to an alarm from a clock at specific time. At first, the awakening is a forced reaction to alarm, but with time the body may start anticipating the alarm and the awakening may at times happen even moments before the alarm - when, effectively, from some reference frames the

alarm may even be interpreted as reaction to anticipation. With increasing relativity in causality, thus, it becomes harder to interpret the synchronization as forced.

In fact, in CR, causality is generally just a special case of synchronization.

2.2 Synchronicity

Synchronicity is any non-forced synchronization of *highly* correlated events (events whose correlation/entanglement goes beyond the localization in space/time).

It can be interpreted as relatively random, pseudo-random or non-random. CR, however, postulates that correlated/entangled phenomena are all connected through associated fields of potential of some scale. Negative excitations (attractors) in this field then (with associated gradients in potential) *guide* correlated events to localize near the points of attractors in space/time.

Note, however, that excitations can be positive - leading to repulsion of correlated events.

This implies there is no such thing as absolute randomness, and any apparent randomness is a consequence of inherent limits in observation. From the above, it is easy to see that other physical fields - such as the gravitational field, represent reduced cases of this general field of entanglement.

Note now that the interpretation of the excitation is relative as well. Take two equal electric charges, for example. Here, from the perspective of any of these charges, the excitation of the other will be interpreted as positive. The same excitation will be interpreted as negative in case of two opposite electric charges. The relativity is scale invariant and exists in more complex excitations/correlations as well. The same person, for example, may repel some people, while attracting other.

Now one can explain why some people experience synchronicity regularly, while others experience it rarely, or never - some people are simply localized with negative excitations, some with positive, and some with neither (or both simultaneously). And these excitations can be of various strength.

Since they are highly correlated with the state of mind, they are highly correlated with consciousness and consciousness itself should probably be interpreted as field excitation (with complexity proportional to excitation strength, which may be, among other things, guiding organismal growth and development through time).

Synchronicity conforms to general oscillation and may differ in frequency, intensity and magnitude. If synchronicity guides local evolution/development

it may be interpreted as genetic.

Non-genetic synchronicity has no apparent significant effects on local evolution and may be considered pseudo-random, similarly to non-intentional synchronization of weakly related events. With increasing frequency, intensity and magnitude, a non-genetic synchronicity, however, may be a precursor to genetic synchronicity.

Correlation of synchronicity with [sub]consciousness by itself does not imply deeper meaning - just as the gravitational attraction between the Earth and the Moon does not imply deeper meaning. Thus, while the evidence strongly suggests synchronicity should not be questioned, any assigned meaning certainly should. That does not imply there is no deeper meaning, certainly not for the one experiencing synchronicity - our consciousness may experience synchronicity, but our subconscious may even mediate it to some degree. Finally, just as the Moon affects the Earth and its development (whether the Earth is asking itself what is the Moon doing here or not), synchronicity too can have a profound effect on those experiencing it.

2.2.1 Frequency of synchronicity

Frequency of synchronicity is a measure of the amount (number) of synchronicity events per a unit of time.

2.2.2 Intensity of synchronicity

The intensity of synchronicity is proportional to number of events synchronized or correlated in a particular event.

2.2.3 Magnitude of synchronicity

The magnitude of synchronicity is a measure of the scale of its effect.

2.3 Signs of synchronicity (signals of synchronicity)

Signs, or signals, of synchronicity, are events correlated with an event in future (e.g., precursor events).

Such signals are omnipresent. However, detection and proper interpretation of signals of synchronicity, generally requires experience and a well-developed sense of synchronicity. —

3 Discontinuities in time

According to CR, physical laws are relatively scale-invariant, but different scales of energy are entangled and often coupled. Also, at times, mathematical operations between different scales such as addition (see CR chapter The Unification: Relativistic time) will be *allowed*. Scales will also at times collapse, and these collapses will be associated with discontinuities.

Such collapses do not happen only in space, they happen in time too. Nature, generally, does not discriminate between space and time as we usually do.

In nature, time is relatively cyclic and usually highly correlated with angular (e.g., orbital) motion at some scale. On large and small scales, behaviour of energy is generally very predictable due to this evident periodicity.

But how random are events in between? Per CR postulates, randomness cannot be absolute, and relative periodicity for relatively equivalent events must exist in certain reference frames.

And this is achieved with non-discriminative treatment of scales. In example, we generally treat one day and one month (periods correlated with angular momenta of large scale bodies) differently.

Adding 2 days to a 30-day month will become a period of 32 days. But nature sometimes/somewhere normalizes cyclic periods of different scale, treating days and months equally, so 2 days + 1 month becomes equal to 3 periods, or 3 quanta of angular momentum.

Thus, relatively equal phenomena occurring in space might appear to us as happening randomly, but from a proper reference frame - they are happening periodically. This is, in example, evident in world wars - they appear periodic from a reference frame treating days, months and years equally[6].

From one perspective, wars create discontinuities in time randomly, from the other, certain discontinuities in cyclic time manifest as wars in space.

The magnitude of synchronicity, or the magnitude of effect in space will be proportional to number of collapsed scales. Consider world wars - they have big effect in space due to collapse of at least 3 scales in time.

4 Suggested and guided evolution

There are no events in reality which are absolutely isolated - not more or less synchronized with other events. Consider synchronization between human species and machines. While entering search terms (or searching) in a search engine one may be guided by the suggestions of the machine. These suggestions may be based on the search history of the individual or global search history of the whole population.

That is an example of chained synchronization (on highest level, person - local machine - remote machine) and guidance through synchronization.

In an anthropocentric view on a universe, synchronizations of this kind are a pinnacle of evolution and any other synchronization which would indicate higher intelligence at work or decrease human significance must be absolutely random. Therefore, one anthropocentric mind will never accept genetic synchronicity as a real phenomenon, before it is forced to abandon the anthropocentric view.

However, synchronicity is a real phenomenon[2], and as such can affect/guide local development. When I ask myself questions about the universes, I am often guided in my searches for answers through synchronicity. Signs of synchronicity can be interpreted as suggestions based on the search *history* of the individual soul or global search *history* of the whole population, but not in the past, rather in the effective local future.

As I have stated elsewhere, effective future of an individual/species is not the actual future of that individual/species. In progressive evolution, it is the past of the more evolved individual/species one is entangled with. The future that is actually yet to manifest locally is not absolutely equal to effective future although the probability of strong variation is generally extremely low in case of strong entanglement - in effect, local evolution is strongly coded or deterministic. Suggestive events of synchronicity that result in local guidance are thus echoes of distant (remote) reactions in time, absorbed and interpreted as action by local reality.

Local excitation (carrying consciousness) coupled to a local body of mass can be interpreted as a soul. Development of a body from conception to adulthood can then be interpreted as an attempt of synchronization [of evolution] of the body and the soul. Excitation (soul) is obviously changing scale between the couplings. At smaller scale it evolves faster, so the coupling slows down its evolution (development), accelerating the evolution (development) of the body. Such couplings do not exist only on the level of individuals, they exist on the level of evolutionary correlated individuals as well (e.g., species, cells of self-organized entities - such as organs, etc.).

One could argue that the soul and the body are one and the same, only the interpretation is scale-dependent. On one scale the entity is interpreted as the mind, on other as the body. However, two interpretations obviously exist simultaneously - at least from our perspective.

Transformation of consciousness is probably highly correlated with the excitation of the soul (consciousness) to a higher energy level, which then should be synchronized with further development of the body - even if mostly on epigenetic basis (possibly including some ageing reversal as well). Indeed, I myself have experienced strong physiological changes, and I believe my life has been prolonged, with such excitation. This elevated level of consciousness has enabled and initiated the construction of CR and *follow-up* works such as the analysis of the Solar System in CR context[7]. The excitation occurred with overwhelming synchronicity,

however, synchronicity eventually stabilized at some lower value - but remained regular, which I correlate with the settling of the soul on the new level.

I consider this excitation to a higher energy level as progressive evolution of the mind-body coupling. One now must ask whether such excitation - that is known to occur in some individuals, is a precursor of the global transformation of species. However, I find the global progressive evolution of minds very questionable. Instead, these might be signals of divergence of humans into different species. In any case, this is such a large difference that even now different[ly excited] humans should probably be classified into different subspecies[3].

5 Global synchronicity

Since changes in synchronicity are highly correlated with excitation of souls and souls are not limited to a single scale (e.g., the scale of those coupled to human brains), changes in synchronicity can be global as well. Indeed, I believe that the current accelerated global changes (including the climate change) are a part of a strong evolution event that will bring the local system to a new equilibrium. Global increase in synchronicity is thus possible. I believe all three (frequency, intensity and magnitude) should be increasing exponentially with a pulse of strong evolution (which, from some perspectives, is interpreted as a major extinction event).

UPDATE: It seems global synchronicity is progressing[8], as predicted. Recently, in South African national lottery, the winning sequence of numbers was: 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10[9].

Now, the probability of drawing this combination of numbers is the same as for any other combination of numbers, but the probability that drawn combination will be a sequence of numbers ordered by value we give to each number (where each n_{th} number is equal to $n+4$) is extremely low. For that reason, there is speculation of fraud. But if one wants to cheat, I assume one would fix a *non-suspicious* combination of numbers, paradoxically then, this *suspicious* combination suggests a lower chance of cheating than usual. Thus, I believe there was no cheating, but it's not an absolute coincidence either.

Note that, by my definition of synchronicity, each win on lottery is an event of synchronicity, but this particular one is much stronger in intensity (20 people won) and magnitude. Additionally, one could argue that the specific draw is, due to high correlation between numbers, an event

of synchronicity itself.

Now, while this synchronicity may have a deeper meaning for those affected (it certainly should have a big effect on their lives and of those about them), does it have any meaning for the global population? Well, this may be a sign (or a precursor) indicating that intensity will be further increasing (as predicted). Does that imply the number of lottery winners will be increasing too? I wouldn't rule it out, at least in some places.

6 Information encoding and consequences of ignorance

Up to this point in human evolution, signals of synchronicity were generally either misinterpreted (inadvertently or not - depending on interests), or dismissed as real events. This is - mainly, both, a consequence of, and a reason for, its ignorance in mainstream science. The ignorance could have serious effects, both for science and individuals. If signals of synchronicity carry information, the relevant information is not necessarily encoded in the synchronization itself, rather in its frequency, intensity and magnitude, or changes (modulation) thereof (just like it is generally the case for propagating information). High intensity/frequency of synchronicity events, per the experience of some individuals (mine included), can certainly *carry* a message. For example, if one doesn't usually experience synchronicity and then becomes suddenly flooded by it, something deeper probably is going on (e.g. transformation of consciousness). To ignore it, or not to ignore it, may be a personal choice, but one probably won't be able to ignore the consequences - a person may choose to ignore the gravity near a black hole, but that does not imply the gravity will ignore the person. In fact, ignorance usually leads to uncomfortable outcomes. If synchronicity is highly correlated with subconsciousness, is it wise to ignore subconsciousness? In the long-term, it could lead to the loss of subconscious (settling of consciousness on a lower energy level), further exacerbating the difference between the more *excited* ones and less *excited* ones. But again, divergence is natural, and may be for the best.

7 Conclusion

It is not hard to understand synchronicity, certainly not in the context of CR. However, it is also not hard to understand that those not experiencing synchronicity will have a hard time accepting it as real. The trouble is, it seems that one has to have an open mind to understand synchronicity and accept it as real, but at the same time, the experience of synchronicity may be limited to

open minds. This synchronization or coupling of mind opening and the experience of synchronicity may be limited to individuals diverging into separate species from established humanity. If we are indeed diverging, science should and probably will diverge as well. Thus, even though the aim of this paper was to shed some light on synchronicity regardless of the state of mind, it may be useless to seek acceptance of the phenomenon of synchronicity (and anything else that significantly deviates from established dogma) in mainstream science. In fact, it could become harder and harder. I, myself, am tired of force, and long for understanding, but this is only a problem until one understands that the majority may simply be wired differently - unable to understand the highly *excited* minds and their experiences. Understanding of synchronicity is then coupled with understanding of open or differently *excited* minds in general. In other words, the sense of synchronicity can be interpreted as a *6th sense* some of us are developing, but some of us may be losing the capability to even contemplate it.

References

- [1] Why Coincidences, Miracles And Rare Events Happen Every Day (2014), J. Navin
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/johnnavin/2014/02/18/why-coincidences-miracles-and-rare-events-happen-every-day/>
- [2] Clock synchronicity experiment (2023), Amenoum
https://completerelativity.org/log/20_clock_synchronicity_experiment.html
- [3] The species of homo (2020), Amenoum
https://completerelativity.org/log/25_species_of_homo.html
- [4] Synchronistic Experience: Enlightenment or Psychosis? (2021), C. Mackey
<https://www.synchronicityunwrapped.com.au/blog/synchronistic-experience-enlightenment-or-psychosis>
- [5] Complete Relativity: Nature of Observables (2021), Amenoum
https://completerelativity.org/complete_relativity.html
- [6] Date of the World War III (2022), Amenoum
<https://completerelativity.org/blog/2022.04.05.html>
- [7] The Solar System: Nature and Mechanics (2021), Amenoum
https://completerelativity.org/solar_system.html
- [8] Evidence of reincarnation and global synchronicity (2022), Amenoum
https://completerelativity.org/log/26_evidence_of_reincarnation.html
- [9] South Africa's lottery probed as 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 drawn and 20 win (2020), BBC News
<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-africa-55154525>